

X-Ray structure determination of tris{1-(methylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-thiolato}antimony(III) complex

K. Hussain Reddy

Department of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract : 1-(Methyl)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol, $\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}$ and 1-(benzylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol, $\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_2\text{Ph})\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}$ form monomeric complexes with Sb^{3+} . The structure of tris{1-(methylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiolato}antimony(III) has been determined by X-ray diffraction study.

Keywords : X-Ray crystallography, antimony(III) complex.

In continuation of our earlier work¹, we report here the synthesis and characterization of antimony(III) complexes with sulfide-thiol ligands viz. 1-(methyl)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (1) and 1-(benzylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (2). The structure of $\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]_3$ was determined by X-ray single crystal diffraction.

Results and discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic, insoluble in water but soluble in chloroform and dichloromethane. Attempts to grow single crystals of sufficient quality for X-ray diffraction were successful only in the case of $\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}]_3$.

The ¹H NMR signals, assignment (number) and shift in ppm (multiplicity) for the ligands and complexes are as follows :

$\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}$, phenyl (10H) 7.190–7.050 (m); CH₃ (3H) 2.141(s); SH (1H) 4.31 (s); $\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_2\text{Ph})\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}$, phenyl (15H) 7.11–7.25 (m); CH₂ (2H)

3.67 (s); SH (1H) 4.34 (s); $\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}]_3$, phenyl (30H) 6.98–7.22 (m); CH₃ (9H) 2.00 (s); $\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_2\text{Ph})\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}]_3$, phenyl (45H) 6.98–7.56 (m); CH₂ (6H) 3.86 (s); $\text{Pb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}]_2$, phenyl (20H) 7.204–6.975 (m); CH₃ (6H) 2.026 (s).

The crystallographic data collection details for $\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}]_3$ are given in experimental section. The molecular structure is shown in Fig. 1 and the important bond lengths and bond angles are listed in Table 2.

The present structure is interesting since it is a novel five coordinate antimony(III) complex. The study reveals that the anions of present facultative bidentate ligands form 5-coordinated complexes with antimony under the conditions where tin reached a higher coordination of eight¹.

Fig. 1. Perspective diagram of $\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}]_3$ with numbering of atoms.

Table 1. Analytical data of ligands and their metal complexes

Compd. (Color)	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)	
		C	H
$\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}$ (Yellow)	67	69.50 (69.75)	5.52 (5.42)
$\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_2\text{Ph})\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}$ (Yellow)	61	75.40 (75.44)	5.42 (5.31)
$\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]_3$ (Orange brown)	145	60.75 (60.40)	4.50 (4.36)
$\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_2\text{Ph})\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}]_3$ (Brown)	132	67.43 (67.86)	5.20 (5.14)

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for Sb[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph]₃

Sb-S(1)	2.461 (1)	S(1)-Sb-S(3)	82.2 (1)
Sb-S(3)	2.492 (1)	S(1)-Sb-S(5)	98.0 (1)
Sb-S(5)	2.446 (1)	S(3)-Sb-S(5)	85.9 (1)
S(1)-C(2)	1.769 (4)	Sb-S(1)-C(2)	106.6 (1)
S(2)-C(1)	1.780 (4)	C(1)-S(2)-C(7)	102.4 (2)
S(2)-C(7)	1.811 (4)	Sb-S(3)-C(3)	99.0 (1)
S(3)-C(3)	1.782 (4)	C(4)-S(4)-C(8)	104.4 (2)
S(4)-C(4)	1.771 (4)	Sb-S(5)-C(5)	108.5 (1)
S(4)-C(8)	1.792 (5)	C(6)-S(6)-C(9)	107.2 (2)
S(5)-C(5)	1.775 (4)	S(2)-C(1)-C(2)	120.4 (3)
S(6)-C(6)	1.765 (4)	S(2)-C(1)-C(11)	115.6 (3)
S(6)-C(9)	1.770 (5)	C(2)-C(1)-C(11)	123.9 (3)
C(1)-C(2)	1.347 (5)	S(1)-C(2)-C(1)	126.3 (3)
C(1)-C(11)	1.488 (5)	S(1)-C(2)-C(21)	111.6 (3)
C(2)-C(21)	1.503 (5)	C(1)-C(2)-C(21)	121.9 (3)
C(3)-C(4)	1.355 (5)	S(3)-C(3)-C(4)	121.8 (3)
C(3)-C(31)	1.495 (5)	S(3)-C(3)-C(31)	114.0 (3)
C(4)-C(41)	1.484 (5)	C(4)-C(3)-C(31)	124.1 (3)
C(5)-C(6)	1.353 (6)	S(4)-C(4)-C(3)	118.9 (3)
C(5)-C(51)	1.489 (6)	S(4)-C(4)-C(41)	116.8 (3)
C(6)-C(61)	1.490 (5)	C(3)-C(4)-C(41)	124.3 (3)
C(11)-C(12)	1.384 (6)	S(5)-C(5)-C(6)	116.5 (3)
C(11)-C(16)	1.390 (5)	S(5)-C(5)-C(51)	118.9 (3)
C(12)-C(13)	1.383 (6)	C(6)-C(5)-C(51)	124.3 (3)
C(13)-C(14)	1.373 (8)	S(6)-C(6)-C(5)	118.3 (3)
C(14)-C(15)	1.375 (7)	S(6)-C(6)-C(61)	118.9 (3)
C(15)-C(16)	1.376 (6)	C(5)-C(6)-C(61)	122.7 (3)
C(21)-C(22)	1.378 (5)	C(1)-C(11)-C(12)	120.4 (3)
C(21)-C(26)	1.390 (6)	C(1)-C(11)-C(16)	121.4 (3)
C(22)-C(23)	1.392 (6)	C(12)-C(11)-C(16)	118.2 (3)
C(23)-C(24)	1.376 (7)	C(11)-C(12)-C(13)	121.4 (4)
C(24)-C(25)	1.362 (7)	C(12)-C(13)-C(14)	119.4 (4)
C(25)-C(26)	1.384 (6)	C(13)-C(14)-C(15)	119.9 (4)
C(31)-C(32)	1.383 (5)	C(14)-C(15)-C(16)	120.6 (4)
C(31)-C(36)	1.400 (5)		
C(32)-C(33)	1.388 (6)	Sb-S(2)	3.013
C(33)-C(34)	1.376 (6)	Sb-S(4)	3.322
C(34)-C(35)	1.379 (6)	Sb-S(6)	5.080
C(35)-C(36)	1.383 (6)		
C(41)-C(42)	1.380 (5)		
C(41)-C(46)	1.387 (5)		
C(42)-C(43)	1.379 (6)		
C(43)-C(44)	1.388 (6)		
C(44)-C(45)	1.360 (7)		

The complex, $\text{Sb}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_2\text{Ph})\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{SH})\text{Ph}]_3$ consists of a Sb metal centre bonded heavily to three thiol-sulphur atoms and moderately to two of the three sulphide-sulphur atoms as evident by bond length data [Sb-S(1) = 2.462; Sb-S(3) = 2.492, Sb-S(5) = 2.44, Sb-S(2) = 3.013, Sb-S(4) = 3.322 Å] resulting in penta-coordinated structure for the complex. The distance between Sb and S(6) is very large (5.080 Å) indicating no bond formation between these atoms. The phenyl rings of the ligands are not planar with each other suggesting no interaction between the aromatic rings. Recently, antimony(III) complexes diarsines are reported to have distorted octahedral structure². Pentagonal bipyramidal structure³ is proposed for amino guanidinium (ethylenediamine, *N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetato)antimonate(III) monohydrate. Thus the survey literature reveals that penta-coordinated antimony(III) complexes are scarce.

Experimental

Solvents used for the preparation of thiols and their antimony(III) complexes were distilled and dried. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade and used as supplied.

1-(Methyl)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (1) and 1-(benzylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (2) were prepared respectively by the reaction of $\text{Ni}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]_2$ -Ni[Ph(SCH₂Ph)C=C(S)Ph]₂ with alkaline NaCN by following the methods described earlier¹.

Antimony complexes : Antimony(III) chloride (0.23 g, 1 mmol) dissolved in minimum amount of water (25 ml) was added dropwise to hot ethanolic solution (2 mmol; 100 ml) of 1-(methyl)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (0.52 g)/1-benzyl-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (0.66 g). The orange-brown coloured solid formed immediately was crystallized from CH₂Cl₂-hexane solvent pair.

The ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded in sealed tubes with a GE-300 NMR instrument at 300 MHz.

X-Ray crystallography :

Crystal data : Empirical formula, C₄₅H₃₉S₆Sb; formula weight, 893.9; crystal system, monoclinic; space

group, *P*2₁/*n* (# 15); symmetry element, C_{2h} : unit cell dimensions, *a* = 12.781(2), *b* = 14.631(0), *c* = 22.148(6), β = 94.000(0)°; volume, 4131.6(13) Å³; Z = 4, density (calcd.), 1.437 Mg/m³; *F*(000) = 1824, μ(MoKα) = 99.3 g cm³.

Measurements were made on a crystal of approximate dimensions (0.22 × 0.28 × 0.40 mm with Simens R 3m/V diffractometer and graphite monochromated MoKα radiation (λ = 0.71072 Å) using 2θ-θ scan mod. scan rate 2.50 to 5.00°/min in omega. Temperature (K) 296, No significant decay of compound during measurements. Lorenz and polarization corrections were applied.

The structure was solved using the Patterson method and refined via full-matrix least squares method using Siemens SHELXTL PLUS (MicroVAX II) programs. The antimony and sulphur atoms were located from Patterson map. Successive different Fourier synthesis and full matrix refinement revealed all other hydrogen atoms. Hydrogen atoms were constrained to their calculated positions using a riding model and refined with fixed isotropic temperature factors. All other atoms were refined anisotropically. Least square weight of the form, σ²(*F*) + 0.0001 *F*² was applied. The longest difference peak 0.53 eÅ⁻³, largest difference hole -0.32 eÅ⁻³. The final data parameter ratio was 8.9 : 1, *R* = 0.0258, *R*_w = 0.0286.

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